

Conference Abstract

Populations state of selected communities of *Juniperus communis* (Common Juniper) in Vitosha Mt., Bulgaria

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Abstract

Juniperus communis L. formations on heaths or calcareous grassland are included in the Bulgarian Biological Diversity Act (code 5130) and some of them are covered by the European Ecological Network Natura 2000 in Bulgaria.

Aim: The purpose of this work is to investigate the status of selected communities with the participation of *J. communis* in the Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) "Vitosha" with an emphasis on the species richness of plants and fungi and the impact of natural and anthropogenic factors.

Material and methods: The survey was conducted between May and September 2019. Habitat 5130 covers an area of 19.27 ha in the territory of SAC "Vitosha". For the purpose of this study is crawled throughout the mountain where it is registered. The route and stationary methods were used for selected objects. Reporting plots were installed in 5 places, each with an area of 100 sq.m. For the assessment of the state of *J. communis*' communities and the influencing factors the appropriate Methodology used for the establishment of the national Natura 2000 network in Bulgaria was applied (Zingstra et al. 2009).

Results: A remarkable species richness of plants and fungi was found in the selected communities of Common Juniper at SAC "Vitosha". A new lignicolous species for the Bulgarian mycota, *Peniophora junipericola* J. Erikss on single host *J. communis*, was found. The explored plant communities were in good condition and have not been established factors threatening their existence.

Conclusion: The habitat occurs at various altitudes and includes species with various ecological characteristics. A tendency for restoration and increasing of the areas covered by the Common juniper has been observed recently as a result of abandonment of arable land.

Keywords

Juniperus communis, Bulgarian flora, SAC, Vitosha Mt.

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